

JUSTIFICATION OF REACTIVE POWER COMPENSATION TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF SUPPLY VOLTAGE OF SUBSTATIONS OF MINING AND PROCESSING PLANTS

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ABSTRACT

Purpose. Justification of rational levels of reactive power compensation to improve the quality of the supply voltage of substations of mining and processing plants. This will reduce both current and voltage harmonics, as well as increase the energy efficiency of synchronous motors involved in reactive power compensation.

Methods. The following were used: data from literary sources and patent documentation in the field of improving the quality of the supply voltage of substations of mining and processing plants, justification of rational levels of reactive power compensation of synchronous motors; laboratory and production experiments ensuring the minimum payment of the enterprise for the reactive power of substations based on existing calculated tariffs; modeling of various options for switching capacitor units.

Findings. It is shown that alternate connection of phases in a three-phase network will reduce the initial current surge on the line by almost 2 times and in the capacitor by almost 3 times. A new method for increasing the energy efficiency of synchronous motors involved in reactive power compensation is recommended for substations with powerful synchronous equipment.

Originality. The main results of modeling using MS Excel software are presented. Modeling of switching on and off stages of compensating devices at substations was performed in Matlab Simulink software. A rational moment of switching on (switching) capacitor units when the current graph passes through zero was determined.

Results. Improving the safety and efficiency of power supply for developing ore mining sites will ensure greater flexibility of the power supply system for mining operations. This method allows reducing sinusoid distortion, through electrical installations in networks of various voltages when expanding the front of mining operations, both underground and open-pit. Large earth fault currents (low total resistance of network insulation) indicate the need to compensate for capacitive currents in 6 kV networks by installing compensating (arc-quenching) reactive coils.

Practical implications. A new method of alternately switching on phases in a three-phase network is recommended, which allows reducing sinusoid distortion and negative impact on the power supply network indicators. The results of the study on the model showed the best quality of the supply voltage of substations of the mining and processing plant of PJSC "Severniiy GOK", Ukraine.

Keywords: mining and processing plant, reactive power, synchronous motor, energy efficiency.

1. Introduction

Technological processes of any production largely depend on the quality of electric power [1, 2]. The quality of energy may depend, in turn, both on the energy supplier and on the nature of the consumer load [3, 4]. The active component of power is usefully used, turning into mechanical, light and other types of energy [5, 6]. The reactive component of power does not perform useful work, it serves to create magnetic fields in inductive receivers, while the electric energy stored in each inductive element is distributed throughout the network, not dissipating in the active elements, but making oscillatory movements (from the load to the generator

and back). The indicator of reactive power consumption Q is the power factor $\cos\varphi = P / S$, which shows the ratio of active power P and apparent power S [7, 8]. The load in industrial networks is usually inductive in nature, which causes the consumption of a significant share of reactive power in addition to active power. The increased, in connection with this, consumed total power leads to the following [9, 10]:

an increase in the payment to the electricity supplier;

additional losses in conductors due to the increase in current and, consequently, a decrease in the transmission capacity of networks;

an overestimation of the power of transformers and cable cross-sections, deviation of the network voltage from the nominal value;

a decrease in the quality of electricity.

2. Formulation of the problem

According to foreign studies, the losses of European countries from poor-quality electric energy annually reach tens of billions of euros. Similar data for Ukraine are currently unavailable, since the problem of electric energy quality is systematically addressed only by scientists, and this despite the fact that losses from poor-quality electric energy tend to grow annually (in the USA, for example, they have doubled over the past ten years).

Also known are the schemes for regulating the reactive power of a power substation with synchronous drive electric:

measuring active and reactive power and measuring the temperature of the stator windings and cooling air;

motors of different rated power, which contain: determining the total power of each motor;

setting or measuring the required reactive power of the electric network and, if the total power, the temperature of the stator windings and the air cooling themotor do not exceed their limit values, including the electric motor in the reactive power regulation process;

determining, for the required value, the reactive power of the electric network and the measured values of the active power of electric motors, the required power of all taking electric motors participation in the regulation.

The disadvantage of such reactive power control schemes is that the calculation of the maximum apparent power of the motors does not take into account the current process parameters significantly affect the accuracy of the devices in terms of assessing their regulating capabilities. reactive power, i.e. determining the real maximum apparent power. For synchronous motors operating in the reactive power control mode, for a more accurate determination of the values of compensating power, it is necessary to provide an analytical determination of the maximum apparent power of each motor, based on the use of real process parameters of operation.

One of the simple and inexpensive ways to eliminate all these network shortcomings is reactive power compensation by connecting capacitors at different points in the network [11]. The most effective compensation devices are automatic reactive power compensation units (APCU), which allow automatic maximum equalization of the consumed and generated reactive power in the system. In addition, the use of powerful semiconductor converters to regulate the parameters of electric motors leads to the appearance of higher harmonic and non-harmonic components of the voltage and current of the network. In practice, filter-compensating devices (FCD) are most often used, performing the functions of reactive power compensation and filtering the components of the parameters of the electric network [12, 13]. Therefore, increasing the efficiency

of the supply voltage of substations of mining and processing plants based on the justification reactive power compensation is an important scientific and practical problem that requires an urgent solution.

The object of the study is substations of mining and processing plants and synchronous motors involved in reactive power compensation, as well as power grids.

The purpose of the study. Determination of rational levels of reactive power compensation to improve the quality of the supply voltage of substations of mining and processing plants, ensuring a reduction in both current and voltage harmonics, as well as increasing the energy efficiency of synchronous motors involved in reactive power compensation.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve the following problems.

1. Perform modeling and consider various options for switching capacitor units in order to assess their negative impact on the power grid.

2. Suggest a method for selecting the power of compensating devices that ensures the minimum payment by the enterprise for reactive power.

3. Recommend the developed method for increasing the energy efficiency of synchronous motors involved in reactive power compensation.

3. Methods

A technological audit and analysis of works in the field of energy efficiency of synchronous motors participating in reactive power compensation and increasing the supply voltage of substations of mining and processing plants were performed. Laboratory experimental studies, mathematical and physical modeling, as well as theoretical analysis and generalization of research results using standard and new methods were carried out. As a result, fuzzy controllers were synthesized and their operation was modeled in the MatLab software package environment. The main modeling results are presented visually using MS Excel software. Modeling was carried out in Matlab Simulink software of switching on and off the stages of compensating devices at substations in order to determine their negative impact on network parameters. Switching of capacitor units often leads to significant overvoltages, especially in networks saturated with higher harmonics [14, 15].

4. Results and discussion

The choice of the compensation level must be decided taking into account the current tariffs for payment of reactive power. The current tariff provides for payment for reactive power consumption during the daytime and payment for consumption and generation of reactive power at night. Based on the daily schedules of reactive power consumption for substations of the

Krivoy Rog, Ukraine), the optimal values of the installed compensating devices were determined to ensure the minimum payment for reactive power. Private Joint Stock Company "Northern Mining and Processing Plant" (PJSC "Northern GOK", For the input of the substation GPP-1 of the plant, synthesized schedules of payment by the enterprise for consumed and generated reactive power are given, the thick line shows the schedule of choosing the capacity of capacitor units to minimize payment for it (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Graphs of changes in the enterprise's payment for consumed and generated reactive power for input 1 GPP-1 in the summer (a) and winter (b) operating periods

The graphs show:

- total payment for reactive power (black line);
- payment for reactive power generation at night (blue line).

As can be seen from the graphs, the total payment for reactive power (black line) has a clearly defined minimum, which indicates the potential for reducing the payment for reactive power [16, 17]. For substations with a powerful synchronous load, where synchronous motors themselves can be used to compensate for reactive power, a new method has been developed to increase the energy efficiency of technical systems with synchronous motors operating in reactive power compensation mode.

Let us consider the problem of overvoltages when using vacuum circuit breakers, taking into account the features of the arc-quenching medium and the design of these devices, as well as the loads they switch. When a load (transformer, electric motor, capacitor bank) is switched on by a correctly designed circuit breaker (not causing contact bounces), its arc-quenching medium

does not play any role in terms of overvoltage occurrence.

Overvoltages in this case are caused by the features of the network and the switched connection as multi-circuit inductive-capacitive circuits, the moment of switching on in time and the spread in the closing of contacts of different phases of the circuit breaker [18].

During transient processes, when capacitors are switched on, short-term current surges occur, which can significantly exceed the rated current (with an amplitude of up to 550%). All this forces us to approach switching processes with special caution [19].

The main causes of overvoltage on the insulation of a separate connection (and only it, not the entire network) when disconnecting the load, associated with the features of the arc-quenching medium and the design of the circuit breaker, are current cutoff and voltage escalation. Let's simulate the connection of a capacitor in a single-phase sinusoidal system at different points in time (Figure 2).

Figure 2.

Model of the capacitor connection system in a single-phase sinusoidal network in the Matlab Simulink software

4.1. Theory of the issue

In accordance with the parameters of reactive power consumption, the optimal power of the compensating unit was established in the report (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Model for studying switching options of capacitor banks

The optimal power of the compensating unit is 3000 kVar. Let us calculate the capacity for setting the model parameters in the Matlab Simulink software according to the formula $Q_c = \frac{U_c^2}{X_c}$. (1). Let's substitute the values of the capacitor's reactive resistance into formula (1): $X_c = \frac{1}{\omega C}$. (2), we get: $Q_c = U_c^2 \cdot \omega C$. (3). From where we determine the calculation formula for the capacitor's capacitance: $C = \frac{Q_c}{U_c^2 \cdot \omega} = \frac{Q_c}{U_c^2 \cdot 2 \cdot \pi \cdot f}$. (4). Given the known initial data included in the calculation formula (4), the capacitance of the capacitor will be equal to: $C = \frac{Q_c}{U_c^2 \cdot 2 \cdot \pi \cdot f} = \frac{3000 \cdot 10^3}{6000^2 \cdot 2 \cdot \pi \cdot 50} = 265 \text{ mкФ}$.

4.2. Simulation results

Calculation examples. Initial data. The conditional parameters of the circuit are as follows: AC Voltage Source: $U = 380\text{V}$, $f = 50\text{Hz}$. Series RLC Branch: $R = 0.01 \text{ Ohm}$; $L = 3.18 \text{ }\mu\text{H}$. Load: $R = 1 \text{ Ohm}$; $L = 10 \text{ }\mu\text{H}$. Series RLC Branch1: $L = 25 \text{ }\mu\text{H}$; $C = 1 \text{ mF}$.

Solution. This model will allow simulating the switching of a capacitor bank at different points in time, resulting in changes in the current on the line (Figure 4, a, b, c), and the current on the capacitor (Figure 5, a, b, c). We will turn on the capacitor at the following points in time: 30 el. deg (0.005/3 sec.); 90 el. deg (0.005 sec.); 180 el. deg (0.01 sec.).

Option 1 (Figure 4, a) - 30 el. deg (0.005/3 sec.). As a result of switching the capacitor on the line, a significant current surge occurred, after which an oscillatory damping process began. The current surge is about

300% of the nominal value, the process damping time is 0.025 sec.

Option 2 (Figure 4, b) - 90 el. deg (0.005 sec.). As a result of switching the capacitor on the line, a significant current surge occurred, which, compared to the previous case (Figure 4, a), is significantly greater. After the surge, a damped oscillatory process began. The current surge is 500% of the nominal value, the process attenuation time is 0.03 sec.

Option 3 (Figure 4, c) - 180 el. deg. (0.01 s). As a result of switching the capacitor, no significant current surges occurred on the line. *Option 3* (Figure 4, c) - 180 el. deg. (0.01 s). As a result of switching the capacitor, no significant current surges occurred on the line.

Option 4 (Figure 5, a) - The current surge is about 1000% of the nominal value, the process attenuation time is 0.03 s. 30 el. deg. (0.005/3 s).

Option 5 (Figure 5, b) - 90 el. deg (0.005 sec.). As a result of switching the capacitor on the line, a significant current surge (1750% of the nominal value) occurred, which is significantly greater than in the previous case (switching on the capacitor at 0.005/3 sec.). After the surge, a damped oscillatory process began [20]. The process damping time is 0.03 sec.

Option 6 (Figure 5, c) - 180 el. deg (0.01 sec.). As a result of switching the capacitor, an insignificant current surge (with an amplitude of up to 150%) occurred on the latter, compared to the previous cases. After the surge, a damped oscillatory process began. The process damping time is 0.03 sec. Having analyzed the graphs of transient processes, we can conclude that the optimal time for switching on the capacitors is the moment when the sinusoid passes through "zero" [21].

a

b

c

Figure 4. Current on the line (Current Measurement) at the moments of switching on: (a) - 30 units deg (0.005/3 sec.); (b) - 90 units deg (0.005 sec.); (c) - 180 units deg (0.01 sec.)

For a network with a frequency of 50 Hz, this moment in time is about 0.01 s.

a

Figure 5. Current on the capacitor (Current Measurement 1) at the moments of switching on: (a) - 30 el. deg (0.005/3 s); (b) - 90 el. deg (0.005 s); (c) - 180 el. deg (0.01s)

Taking into account the obtained results, we will simulate the switching on of several stages of capacitors in a three-phase system. To calculate and set the model parameters, we use the data for June 2019 for GPP-1t Sh2 ROF1. According to the data for June 2019, the following parameters of the circuit were set:

Three-Phase Series RLC Load: $P=8.50$ MW;
 $Q=2.87$ MVar;

Three-Phase Source: $U=6$ kV; $f=50$ Hz;

Three-Phase Series RLC Branch: $R=1$ $\mu\Omega$; $L=1$ μH .

To determine the optimal compensating capabilities for the reactive power of synchronous motors, which will increase the efficiency of the system, its reliability and service life, the authors propose measuring the voltage supplying the electric motor and the current temperature of the cooling motor at discrete time intervals. Their values are used to calculate the maximum apparent power of each motor involved in the compensation mode. The obtained data are compared with the actual measured reactive power of the electric motor and the excitation current of the motor is changed. The required value of reactive power is achieved by each electric motor, with the same load at full power.

Option 7. Initial data. Parameters of the units: Series RLC Branch 1, Series RLC Branch 3, Series RLC Branch 7: $C=265$ μF . Parameters of the current-limiting reactor: RLC Branch 2, Series RLC Branch 4, Series RLC Branch 5: $L=1$ mH. Simultaneous connection of capacitors (0.01 s). Solution. As a result of switching the capacitor on the line, a significant current surge (with an amplitude of up to 660%) occurred. You can also see a clearly expressed non-sinusoidality of the current, which indicates the presence of harmonics (Figure 6, a). The presence of the latter is highly undesirable. Harmonic series of current on the capacitor line. Phase A (Ia2) (Figure 6, b). Analyzing the harmonic series for phase A, we can conclude that the most significant in amplitude are the 1st and 6th harmonics. The coefficient of non-sinusoidality at the end of the transient process is within the normal range and is about 0.53%. Analyzing the harmonic series for each phase, we can conclude that the most significant in amplitude are the 1st and 6th harmonics. The coefficient of non-sinusoidality at the end of the transient process for each phase is within the normal range and is about 0.39%. You can also see a clearly expressed non-sinusoidality of the current, which indicates the presence of unwanted harmonics [24, 25].

Figure 6. Current with simultaneous switching on of capacitor banks (phase A - yellow, B - green, C - red): a - on the phase line (I_{a0}); b - on the capacitor (I_{a2})

Harmonic series of line current after switching on batteries (Figure 7, a).

Figure 7. Harmonic series for current after the end of transient processes with simultaneous inclusion of capacitors: a - phase A; b - capacitor of phase A

Analyzing the harmonic series for phase A, we can conclude that the most significant in amplitude are the 1st and 6th harmonics. The non-sinusoidality coefficient at the end of the transient process is within the normal range and is about 1.18%.

As a result of switching the circuit, a significant current surge (with an amplitude of up to 600 A) occurred on the capacitor. Series connection of capacitors (Figure 8). As a result of switching the capacitor on the line, a minor current surge (with an amplitude of up to 125%) occurred. You can also see a clearly expressed non-sinusoidality of the current, which indicates the presence of harmonics [26, 27].

Harmonic series of the current on the line after switching on the batteries. As a result of switching the circuit on the capacitor, a significant current surge (with an amplitude of up to 200%) occurred. You can also see a clearly expressed non-sinusoidality of the current, which indicates the presence of unwanted harmonics. As a result of the modeling, we can conclude that the alternate switching on of the phases in a three-phase network will reduce the initial current surge on the line by almost 2 times and in the capacitor by almost 3 times.

Figure 8. Current when capacitor banks are connected in series (phase A - yellow, B - green, C - red): a - on the phase line (I_{a0}); b - on the capacitor (I_{a2})

Another advantage of alternate switching is that this method allows you to slightly reduce the distortion of the sinusoid. Switching of capacitor units leads to the presence of both current and voltage harmonics, and, as research results show, they can have a significant impact on the network parameters. The presence of harmonics is an extremely undesirable phenomenon that must be subsequently eliminated.

Based on the modeling results, the choice of harmonics for their subsequent suppression should be selected based on the switching method of capacitor banks [28, 29].

Thus, the authors have developed at the level of a Ukrainian patent [30, 31], a new technological scheme for increasing the energy efficiency of technical systems of process units with synchronous drives by regulating their reactive power, which have been tested at mining and processing plants, in particular, at PJSC SevGOK, Krivoy Rog, Ukraine.

To determine the optimal compensating capabilities for the reactive power of synchronous motors, which will increase the efficiency of the system, its reliability and service life, the voltage supplying the electric motor and the current temperature of the cooling motor are measured at discrete time intervals, the values of which are used to calculate the maximum apparent power of each motor involved in the compensation mode. The obtained data are compared with the actual measured indicators of the reactive power of the electric motor and the excitation current of the motor is changed. The required value of reactive power is achieved by each electric motor, with the same load at full power [32, 33].

Improving the safety and efficiency of power supply for developing ore mining sites will ensure greater flexibility of the power supply system for mining operations. This method allows reducing sinusoid distortion, through electrical installations in networks of various voltages when expanding the front of mining operations, both underground and open-pit. Large earth fault currents (low total resistance of network insulation) indicate the need to compensate for capacitive currents in 6 kV networks by installing compensating (arc-quenching) reactive coils [34, 35].

Based on the obtained scientific and practical results in substantiating reactive power compensation and improving the quality of the supply voltage of substations of mining and processing plants, the authors made the following conclusions [36].

5. Conclusions

Modeling has been performed and various switching options for capacitor banks have been considered in order to assess their negative impact on the power grid. Alternating switching on of phases in a three-phase grid will reduce the initial current surge on the line by almost 2 times and in the capacitor by almost 3 times. This method also reduces sinusoidal distortion.

A rational moment for switching on (switching) capacitor banks that provides the best network parameter indicators has been determined. This moment is the moment the current graph passes through zero. Studies on the model confirm a reduction in the impact of higher harmonic parameters of the power grid.

It has been established that a new method for increasing the efficiency of synchronous motors involved in reactive power compensation is recommended for substations with powerful synchronous equipment. This method is protected by a patent of Ukraine (Patent of Ukraine No. 141771) [28].

A method for selecting the power of compensating devices is proposed, ensuring the minimum payment of the enterprise for reactive power based on daily schedules of reactive power consumption of substations of the enterprise PJSC "SevGOK", Ukraine, existing calculated tariffs.

Further development of algorithms for the reactive power regulator and options for suppressing overvoltage of energy-intensive consumers is recommended in order to improve the efficiency of the supply voltage of mining substations.

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